

Triazoloquinazolines. Part-3. Synthesis and Biological Activity of some 2-Aryl-3-acetyl-2,3-dihydrotriazoloquinazolines

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Synthesis of some new 3-acetyl-2,3-dihydrotriazoloquinazolines (4a-g) and their biological activity are reported.

Syntheses of various heterocycles derived from quinazoline having pharmacological activities have been reported¹. In view of these and in continuation of our earlier work on synthesis and biological activity of a few [4,3-c]- and [1,5-c]triazoloquinazolines², we report here some new 2-aryl-3-acetyl-2,3-dihydrotriazoloquinazolines. Isomerisation of *s*-triazolo[4,3-*c*]quinazolines to [1,5-*c*]quinazolines under acid, base or heat have been reported³ earlier. Similarly, 4-quinazolinylhydrazones (3a-g)

when refluxed with acetic anhydride yielded the titled compounds (4a-g). The formation of compounds 4 from 3 have been proved on the basis of nmr spectrum. The proton at 2-position in compounds 4 shows absorption more upfield than its precursor 3. Compounds 4a-g were converted to the corresponding 5a-g by FeCl₃ oxidation, whose structures have been identified by comparison with the compounds reported earlier². The sequence of the reactions and various aldehydes used⁴ for synthesis are presented in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Experimental

All the m.ps. are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 599-B spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a Varian instrument (360 MHz). All the elemental analyses were found to be satisfactory.

4-Quinazolinylhydrazones (3a-g) were prepared by refluxing the corresponding aldehydes (2a-g) with hydrazinoquinazoline (1) in methanol. The hydrazones (3a-g) were crystallised from suitable solvents.

2-Aryl-3-acetyl-2,3-dihydro-1,2,4-triazolo[1,5-*c*]quinazolines (4a-g): The corresponding 3a-g (0.0032 mol) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (5 cm³) for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured on ice-water. The solution was extracted with methylene chloride, washed with sodium carbonate, dried and concentrated. The resulting solid was recrystallised from suitable solvent, yields 50–57% (Table 1).

2-Aryl-1,2,4-triazolo[1,5-*c*]quinazolines (5a-g): The corresponding 4a-g (0.0022 mol) was added to a solution of FeCl₃·6H₂O (0.005 mol) in water (10 cm³). The solution was heated at 100° for 5 h. After removal of the insoluble salts, the hot solution was allowed to stand at room temperature. The resulting solids were recrystallised from suitable solvents. The m.ps., m.m.ps. and tlc data were comparable with the [1,5-*c*]triazoloquinazolines reported earlier².

TABLE 1—M.P. AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4a—g*

Compd. no.	M.p.** °C	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹	δ
4a	277 ^a	1 620, 1 610, 1 570, 1 520, 1 470, 1 410	2.5 (3H, s, NCOCH ₃), 8.02 (1H, s, H-2), 7.6–9.3 (9H, m, ArH)
b	185 ^b	1 650, 1 620, 1 570, 1 510, 1 480, 1 450	2.2 (3H, s, NCOCH ₃), 7.2–9.8 (13H, m, H-2+ArH)
c	255	1 630, 1 600, 1 560, 1 520, 1 480, 1 400	2.2 (3H, s, NCOCH ₃), 7.92 (1H, s, H-2), 7.0–9.4 (8H, m, ArH)
d	180	1 650, 1 630, 1 570, 1 500, 1 460, 1 440, 1 420	2.2 (3H, s, NCOCH ₃), 7.34 (1H, s, H-2), 6.5–7.9 (8H, m, ArH)
e	182	1 640, 1 580, 1 450, 1 410	2.22 (3H, s, NCOCH ₃), 7.28 (1H, s, H-2), 7.4–7.9 (9H, m, ArH)
f	209	1 670, 1 630, 1 610, 1 580, 1 510, 1 480, 1 410	1.86 (3H, s, NCOCH ₃), 2.2 (3H, s, NCOCH ₃), 2.28 (3H, s, NCOCH ₃), 7.14 (1H, s, H-2), 7.2–7.8 (10H, m, ArH)
g	271	1 700, 1 630, 1 580, 1 480	2.0 (3H, s, NCOCH ₃), 3.8 (3H, s, NCOCH ₃), 7.4–8.2 (10H, m, H-2+ArH)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses. **Solvent for crystallisation: ^amethanol, ^bacetonitrile.

Biological activity: Compounds 4a–g were evaluated for their antibacterial activity by ditch-plate technique⁶ using concentration levels 2 and 5 mg ml⁻¹. The test organisms employed were *Salmonella typhi*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus subtilis*. All the compounds were found to be inactive.

References

1. I. POSTOVSKII, *Khim. Geterotsikl Soedin*, 1966, 130 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1966, 65, 710); G. SIDHU and N. RAO,

- Naturwissenschaften*, 1963, 100, 732; W. RIED and J. VALENTIN, *Chem. Ber.*, 1968, 101, 2106; K. T. POTTS and C. HIRSH, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, 33, 143.
2. M. A. LIKHATE and P. S. FERNANDES, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, communicated; M. A. LIKHATE and P. S. FERNANDES, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, 67, 862.
3. K. T. POTTS, H. R. BURTON and S. K. ROY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, 31, 265; K. T. POTTS and S. W. SCHNELLER, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1968, 5, 485; K. T. POTTS and E. G. BRUGEL, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1970, 35, 3448.
4. M. A. LIKHATE and P. S. FERNANDES, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, 67, 609.
5. C. H. COLLINS and P. M. LYNE, "Microbiological Methods", 3rd. ed., Butterworths, London, 1970, p. 424.